

OPTION FOR MODERNIZING THE TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCING VINYL CHLORIDE FROM ETHANE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13863340>

Abstract. *This article presents a variant of modernization of the technology of obtaining vinyl chloride from ethane and hydrogen chloride and proposes to use the technology of producing high-quality vinyl chloride to meet the daily needs of consumers.*

Keywords: *ethane, hydrogen chloride, vinyl chloride, 1,2-dichloroethane, dehydrochlorination, thermal cracking.*

INTRODUCTION

Vinyl chloride is a unique and most multi-ton product in the chemical industry of complex processing of mineral and organic raw materials. Vinyl chloride production in Russia is almost entirely (more than 99% of the total volume) focused on the production of polyvinyl chloride, the consumption of which in industry is growing every year. Accordingly, the demand for high-quality and cheaper vinyl chloride is increasing, which makes the search for intensification and modernization of its production technology relevant.

As an example of the study, the process of obtaining vinyl chloride is selected, which consists of 2 stages:

Obtaining vinyl chloride from 1,2-dichloroethane by thermal cracking in furnaces at a temperature of 350-500°C and a pressure of 0.8-1.2 MPa. Structural and functional analysis of the selected production allowed us to identify a number of significant shortcomings [1-3]: 1) high process temperature, resulting in the formation of by-products (1,3-butadiene, chloroprene, etc.), which leads to low selectivity for vinyl chloride and low conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane (62-65%); 2) deposition of by-products (coke and resin) on the walls of the reactor (furnace) coils worsens its performance, which leads to frequent shutdowns for cleaning; 3) irrational use of heat from the contact gas leaving the furnace; 4) energy intensity of the synthesis and isolation stages of vinyl chloride; 5) the presence of non-recyclable production waste - resin and coke.

The study of modern global trends in the development of the process of obtaining vinyl chloride and a deep patent information search made it possible to find an option for modernizing the production under study. The essence of the chosen direction is the catalytic dehydrochlorination of 1,2-dichloroethane in a mixture with hydrogen and an inert diluent gas at a temperature of 250-375°C, taken in a molar ratio of 0.01-0.08:0.94-1.18, respectively, in the presence of a silicate applied to a carbon carrier of the AGN brand as a catalytic system. The selected method allows to reduce the process temperature to 250-375°C; significantly reduce the intensity of coke formation processes; obtain selectivity of vinyl chloride formation exceeding 94%; increase dichloroethane conversion to 99.7%, which significantly exceeds the indicators of the industrial analogue [4-6].

The study of the new method, its thermodynamic analysis, consideration of the mechanism and kinetics of the reaction allowed to select the reactor design for the industrial process. A shell-and-tube reactor with a fixed catalyst bed in the tubes was selected. When forming the technological concept, requirements for the stages of raw material preparation and target product isolation were developed [7-9]. At the stage of raw material preparation, it is necessary to evaporate the required amount of 1,2-dichloroethane and heat the vapors to a temperature at least 200°C, and also ensure their mixing with hydrogen in a given molar ratio before feeding into the reactor.

The above requirements for the stages of synthesis and preparation of raw materials make it possible to form a technological scheme for the process of obtaining vinyl chloride by dehydrochlorination of 1,2-dichloroethane (Fig. 1).

Dichloroethane rectified from a tank located in the storage facility is fed by pump NA into the tube space of heat exchangers TE-1 and TE-2, where it evaporates and heats up to a temperature of at least 200°C. Superheated dichloroethane vapors are mixed with hydrogen in a mixing tee before entering the RE reactor in a molar ratio of 0.01-0.08:0.94-1.18, respectively. The dichloroethane-hydrogen mixture enters the reactor tubes filled with catalyst. The temperature regime of 250-375°C is maintained by feeding a high-temperature organic coolant into the intertube space of the reactor, circulating through the PE furnace. The PE furnace operates by burning the outgoing combustible gas (the flow is not shown in Fig. 1). The contact gas leaving the reactor consists of vinyl chloride, hydrogen chloride, unreacted dichloroethane, hydrogen and ethylene (by-product). The contact gas from the RE reactor is fed through the injection nozzle to the quenching section of the quenching column KK into a layer of liquid dichloroethane. As a result of injection of liquid dichloroethane into the layer and sharp expansion, the temperature of the gas mixture drops sharply and the reaction of decomposition of dichloroethane stops. The quenching column consists of two parts - quenching and washing. The quenching part is a cube filled with liquid dichloroethane, where the cracking reaction stops due to sharp cooling of the cracking products. In the washing section, the gases are freed from dichloroethane. The flow is then directed to purification from hydrogen chloride and the separation of vinyl chloride [10-11].

The developed technological concept for the production of vinyl chloride was calculated using the AspenTech HYSYS 2006 software package, taking into account the kinetic model. This calculation made it possible to determine the reactor parameters, thermal load, required catalyst volume, and also to calculate the reaction rate and contact gas temperature at the outlet. Thus, for the production of 100 tons/day of vinyl chloride, a reactor with a volume of 14 m³ (480 tubes 6 m long and 0.08 m in internal diameter) is required. The achieved conversion of 1,2-dichloroethane is 99%, the product yield is not less than 98%, the contact gas temperature at the reactor outlet is 365°C.

Fig. 1. Technological scheme of vinyl chloride production

Thus, the proposed option for modernizing vinyl chloride production by switching to catalytic cracking of 1,2-dichloroethane will allow for a significant reduction in energy costs for the process, increase the specific productivity of the reactor, and improve the quality of the resulting product. Calculations in the AspenTech HYSYS 2006 program revealed the real possibilities of implementing the catalytic process in industry using standard equipment.

Direct chlorination

Chlorine gas is completely dissolved in a relatively small circulating side stream discharged into the down comer of the recirculation loop and is cooled to increase the solubility of the chlorine.

Chlorine is added to this side stream through an injection nozzle. In the reaction zone of the riser, the two solutions are mixed and the already dissolved chlorine and ethylene react to form EDC in a fast liquid phase reaction, which significantly reduces the formation of by-products.

Due to the low static pressure in the upper part of the riser, the EDC starts to boil. The resulting product and some excess EDC are removed from the evaporation tank and sent to the product tank and to the stripper-evaporator to achieve the quality of the commercial EDC, if necessary. Excess EDC is sent back to the main circuit of the reactor.

Thus, the Vinnolit technology combines the efficient use of high-temperature chlorination (HTC) energy with the purity of EDC typical of low-temperature chlorination (LTC). The catalyst is fed into the reactor circuit before start-up and no more is added during normal operation. The resulting dichloroethane is fed directly to the pyrolysis furnace.

Unlike traditional direct chlorination methods, the Vinnolit process uses a complex inorganic compound as a catalyst rather than FeCl_3 . The catalyst suppresses the formation of by-products and provides higher selectivity for EDC.

In the direct chlorination process, EDC is produced through a highly exothermic reaction of ethylene with chlorine.

Vinnolit's direct chlorination technology uses either a traditional reactor or a boiling reactor at temperatures from 80 to 120 °C and pressures from 1 to 2.5 bar abs. The actual temperature depends on the plant concept.

When using boiling reactor technology, the main innovation is an innovative boiling reactor with a convection flow of natural circulation in the outer circuit of the reactor. The reaction takes place in the riser of the Y-shaped circuit. Unlike other technologies, gaseous ethylene is already completely dissolved in the lower part of the riser. The technology is particularly environmentally friendly because fewer high-boiling fractions are formed; an insignificant number of low-boiling components are formed (only a few ppm); there is no need for wash water; there is no removal of catalyst with the product.

Due to its complex structure, the catalyst does not cause corrosion, so carbon steel process equipment can be used. Existing installations can be easily re-equipped.

The advantages of the technology are as follows: almost no catalyst consumption; high yield of EDC; high purity of crude EDC: 99.9%; use of reaction heat, for example, for heating distillation columns, as a result of which steam consumption per ton of EDC is reduced by 0.6 tons.

One of the disadvantages of the above-described process flow chart for obtaining vinyl chloride is its multi-stage nature. Significant difficulties are associated with the process of thermal dehydrochlorination of dichloroethane due to the consumption of a large amount of heat and the

formation of by-products: acetylene, butadiene, chloroprene, as well as intensive resin and coke formation.

Fig. 2. Direct chlorination using a boiling reactor

A natural way to reduce the activation energy and, accordingly, the process temperature is to use catalysts. In addition, the most balanced process has the hidden possibility of using the heat of the exothermic reaction of ethylene oxychlorination (238.8 kJ/mol) to carry out the endothermic reaction of dichloroethane dehydrochlorination (71.2 kJ/mol). Obviously, it is possible to combine these processes in one reaction zone or balance them in terms of heat exchange.

The basic technological scheme of the combined process is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Basic flow chart of the combined process of producing vinyl chloride from ethylene
 1 - reactor; 2 - waste heat boiler; 3 - quenching column; 4, 9 - coolers; 5, 10 - separators; 6, 8, 14 - collectors; 7 - mixer; 11 - scrubber; 12 - absorption column.

Streams: I - ethylene; II - hydrogen chloride; III - air; IV – water; V – steam; VI – drain; VII – alkaline solution; VIII – NaOH; IX – dichloroethane for cleaning; X – exhaust gases; XI – dichloroethane; XII – a mixture of dichloroethane and vinyl chloride.

The combined process of obtaining vinyl chloride takes place in a shell-and-tube reactor on a fixed catalyst bed. Ethylene, hydrogen chloride and air heated to 423 K are fed into reactor 1, filled with catalyst, under a pressure of 0.4 MPa. The reaction takes place at 623 K.

During the reaction in reactor 1, heat is released, for the removal of which a coolant is supplied to the intertube space. The coolant is regenerated in the waste heat boiler 2. The reaction gases leaving the reactor, containing organic products (vinyl chloride, 1,2-dichloroethane, ethyl chloride, dichloroethylene, etc.), carbon oxides, water vapor, nitrogen and unreacted ethylene, hydrogen chloride, oxygen at 623 K enter the bottom of the quenching column 3. The temperature of the gases in the column decreases to 383-393 K.

Cooled and neutralized gases from the upper part of quenching column 3 enter condenser 4, where partial condensation of moisture and dichloroethane occurs. Condensate enters phase separation apparatus 5, from which dichloroethane is sent to raw dichloroethane collector 8, and water to mixer 7 for preparing alkali solution. The gas stream containing vinyl chloride, ethylene, non-condensed organic products, moisture, and inert gases enters the cooler 9, where it is cooled to 278 K, passes through the separator 10 and scrubber 11, where it is dried to a moisture content of 10-20 parts per million, and is then sent to the absorption column 12. With a total conversion of ethylene to vinyl chloride of 89%, the process becomes competitive with the traditional balanced process.

REFERENCES

1. Способ получения винилхлорида и каталитическая система для его осуществления: пат. 2338736. Россия. МПК С07 С21/06. ООО НИИЦ «Синтез». № 2007121604/04 / Е. А. Глазунова, Ю. А. Трегер, М. Р. Флид и др. Заявл. 09.06.2007. Опубл. 20.11.2008. Рус.
2. Юлдашев Т., Дўскобилов Э., Рахматов Х., Юлдашев Н. Нефт ва газни қайта ишлаш технологияси: 1-қисм. ОТМ учун дарслик. Тошкент: Voris-nashriyoti. 2020. 570 б.
3. Принципы технологии основного органического и нефтехимического синтеза : учеб. пособ. для вузов / В. С. Тимофеев, Л. А. Серафимов. М.: Высш. шк., 2003. 536 с.
4. Трегер Ю. А. Винилхлорид: химия и технология: в 2-х т. / Ю. А. Трегер, М. Р. Флид. М.: Калвис, 2008. Т. 1. 581 с.
5. Флид М.Р. Ресурсосберегающие, сбалансированные по хлору технологии получения винилхлорида из этан-этиленового сырья: дисс. докт. техн. наук. М.: МИТХТ, 2002.
6. Яковенко Д. Ю. Изучение промышленного производства получения хлористого винила с помощью структурнофункционального анализа // Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов. 2011. № 2. С. 75-78.
7. Buronov, F. E., & Fayzullaev, N. I. (2023). Mathematical modeling of ethylene oxidative acetylation process. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 411, p. 01037). EDP Sciences.
8. Buronov, F., & Fayzullayev, N. (2022, June). Synthesis and application of high silicon zeolites from natural sources. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2432, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
9. Ortikov, N., Fayzullaev, N., Hamidov, D., & Buronov, F. (2023). Study of methane carbonate conversion process in fixed catalyst layer in different membrane reactors. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 402, p. 14013). EDP Sciences.
10. Fayzullayev N. I. "Optimization process of gas chromatographic separation products of catalytic synthesis of vinyl chloride." Abstracts of papers of the american chemical society. vol. 224. 1155 16th st, nw, Washington, DC 20036 USA: Amer Chemical SOC, 2002.
11. Akmalaiuly K. and Fayzullayev N. "Heterogeneo-catalytic synthesis of vinyl chloride and chloroprene from acetylene." Известия НАН РК. Серия химии и технологии 5 (2020): 5-13.